

M_t or not M_t: Temporal variation in detection probability in spatial capture-recapture and occupancy models

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Appendix 3: Detailed results of occupancy case study of Swiss breeding birds

Table S1: Bird species included in occupancy case study (common and Latin name), total number of detections across 266 sites and 2-3 occasions (n) and naïve occupancy (Occu, number of sites with detections/266). Extracted from Swiss breeding bird data (Schmid et al. 2004) for 2014 from AHMbook v. 0.2.6 (Kéry et al. 2022).

Species	Latin name	n	Occu
Common swift	<i>Apus apus</i>	94	0.21
Common house martin	<i>Delichon urbicum</i>	101	0.2
Whinchat	<i>Saxicola rubetra</i>	52	0.1
Garden warbler	<i>Sylvia borin</i>	161	0.38
Lesser whitethroat	<i>Sylvia curruca</i>	117	0.24
Wood warbler	<i>Phylloscopus sibilatrix</i>	60	0.13
Spotted flycatcher	<i>Muscicapa striata</i>	161	0.4
European pied flycatcher	<i>Ficedula hypoleuca</i>	87	0.19
Red-backed shrike	<i>Lanius collurio</i>	80	0.18
Citril finch	<i>Carduelis citrinella</i>	64	0.13

Table S2: Average site-level ratio of maximum to minimum detection probability p (p.max:p.min) from occupancy model M_{st} (accounting for spatial and temporal variability in p); maximum (D.max) difference between occupancy predictions for sampled locations under model M_s (accounting only for spatial variability in p) and M_{st} (positive values: predictions under M_s are higher); and ΔAIC between M_s and M_{st} (positive values: M_{st} is favored; negative values: M_s is favored) for 10 bird species surveyed in 2014 throughout Switzerland.

Species	p.max:p.min	D.max	ΔAIC
Common swift	89.05	0.13	96.4
Common house martin	2.51	0.04	29.79
Whinchat	7.09	0.02	6.86

Garden warbler	6.93	0.08	71.09
Lesser whitethroat	11.9	0.14	-4.61
Wood warbler	5.06	0.08	6.47
Spotted flycatcher	19.32	0.11	118.81
European pied flycatcher	17.67	0.04	29.4
Red-backed shrike	17.34	0.03	54.79
Citril finch	2.02	0.05	1.3

Table S3: Occupancy model parameter estimates (intercept and coefficients for elev = elevation, elev² = elevation², and forest = percent forest cover) for the state component under M_{st} and M_s: estimates (Est.) with standard errors (SE) and lower (L) and upper (U) 95% confidence interval (CI) limits for both models, with relative difference, (M_s-M_{st})/M_{st}, for 10 bird species surveyed in 2014 throughout Switzerland (note that for all species and parameters, estimates under M_s were within the 95%CI of the corresponding estimate under M_{st}).

<i>Common Swift</i>									
	M _{st}				M _s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff
(Intercept)	-1.11	0.29	-1.68	-0.53	-0.91	0.32	-1.54	-0.29	-0.18
elev	-1.15	0.26	-1.67	-0.64	-1.26	0.3	-1.85	-0.68	0.1
elev ²	-0.75	0.33	-1.4	-0.09	-0.74	0.37	-1.46	-0.02	0
forest	-0.89	0.23	-1.34	-0.43	-1.03	0.27	-1.56	-0.51	0.17
<i>Common House Martin</i>									
	M _{st}				M _s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff
(Intercept)	-0.82	0.3	-1.41	-0.23	-0.78	0.31	-1.38	-0.17	-0.06
elev	-1.28	0.32	-1.91	-0.65	-1.33	0.33	-1.98	-0.69	0.04
elev ²	-1.31	0.4	-2.1	-0.52	-1.32	0.41	-2.13	-0.51	0.01
forest	-1.17	0.27	-1.7	-0.64	-1.2	0.28	-1.76	-0.65	0.03
<i>Whinchat</i>									
	M _{st}				M _s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff
(Intercept)	-1.81	0.38	-2.56	-1.06	-1.75	0.39	-2.52	-0.98	-0.03
elev	2.76	0.76	1.27	4.25	2.7	0.78	1.17	4.22	-0.02
elev ²	-2.01	0.54	-3.06	-0.95	-1.96	0.55	-3.03	-0.89	-0.02
forest	-1.16	0.34	-1.83	-0.48	-1.19	0.35	-1.88	-0.5	0.03
<i>Garden Warbler</i>									
	M _{st}				M _s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff

(Intercept)	0.79	0.31	0.18	1.4	0.95	0.35	0.26	1.64	0.2
elev	-0.06	0.18	-0.4	0.29	0	0.2	-0.39	0.39	-0.99
elev ²	-0.97	0.25	-1.47	-0.48	-0.98	0.28	-1.53	-0.43	0.01
forest	-0.5	0.19	-0.88	-0.12	-0.58	0.21	-1	-0.16	0.16
Lesser Whitethroat									
	M_{st}				M_s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff
(Intercept)	-1.37	0.36	-2.08	-0.67	-0.81	0.4	-1.58	-0.03	-0.41
elev	3.66	0.71	2.28	5.05	2.78	0.72	1.38	4.18	-0.24
elev ²	-1.48	0.44	-2.34	-0.62	-1.09	0.48	-2.02	-0.16	-0.26
forest	0.12	0.24	-0.36	0.6	0.16	0.26	-0.35	0.67	0.35
Wood Warbler									
	M_{st}				M_s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff
(Intercept)	-1.16	0.36	-1.85	-0.46	-0.94	0.38	-1.68	-0.2	-0.19
elev	-2.8	0.94	-4.64	-0.97	-2.29	0.98	-4.21	-0.37	-0.18
elev ²	-3.55	1	-5.51	-1.59	-3.18	1.01	-5.15	-1.21	-0.1
forest	0.69	0.25	0.19	1.18	0.68	0.26	0.16	1.19	-0.01
Spotted Flycatcher									
	M_{st}				M_s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff
(Intercept)	0.46	0.33	-0.18	1.09	0.86	0.46	-0.04	1.75	0.89
elev	-1.42	0.26	-1.94	-0.9	-1.59	0.42	-2.41	-0.77	0.12
elev ²	-0.64	0.34	-1.3	0.03	-0.65	0.44	-1.52	0.22	0.02
forest	0.02	0.23	-0.42	0.47	0.07	0.31	-0.54	0.69	1.92
European Pied Flycatcher									
	M_{st}				M_s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff
(Intercept)	-1.38	0.38	-2.12	-0.64	-1.17	0.4	-1.95	-0.38	-0.16
elev	-4.19	1.11	-6.36	-2.03	-3.9	1.15	-6.17	-1.64	-0.07
elev ²	-3.27	0.93	-5.09	-1.46	-3.12	0.95	-4.97	-1.26	-0.05
forest	0.26	0.21	-0.16	0.67	0.21	0.22	-0.23	0.65	-0.17
Red-backed Shrike									
	M_{st}				M_s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff
(Intercept)	-0.84	0.29	-1.4	-0.28	-0.75	0.3	-1.34	-0.17	-0.11
elev	-0.51	0.23	-0.97	-0.06	-0.57	0.24	-1.04	-0.1	0.11
elev ²	-0.76	0.31	-1.37	-0.15	-0.8	0.31	-1.41	-0.18	0.05
forest	-0.09	0.2	-0.48	0.3	-0.08	0.2	-0.48	0.32	-0.13
Citril Finch									
	M_{st}				M_s				
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U	Diff
(Intercept)	-1.23	0.44	-2.1	-0.36	-1.2	0.45	-2.08	-0.32	-0.03

elev	5.56	1.46	2.69	8.42	5.65	1.5	2.71	8.58	0.02
elev ²	-4.55	1.15	-6.8	-2.3	-4.56	1.18	-6.86	-2.25	0
forest	-0.45	0.27	-0.98	0.08	-0.51	0.28	-1.07	0.05	0.13

Table S4: Occupancy model parameter estimates (intercept and coefficients for date = Julian date starting April 1, date², and dur = survey duration in minutes) for the detection component under M_{st} and M_s; note that under M_{st}, date and dur are incorporated at the site-occasion level, whereas under M_s, the site-level averages (over occasions) are used as predictors. Estimates (Est.) with standard errors (SE) and lower (L) and upper (U) 95% confidence interval (CI) limits for both models, for 10 bird species surveyed in 2014 throughout Switzerland.

<i>Common Swift</i>								
	M _{st}				M _s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	1.74	0.37	1.01	2.47	0.59	0.34	-0.07	1.26
date	2.12	0.4	1.33	2.91	0.56	0.3	-0.02	1.14
date ²	-1.48	0.36	-2.19	-0.78	-0.57	0.33	-1.21	0.07
dur	0.06	0.32	-0.57	0.69	0.28	0.21	-0.13	0.69
<i>Common House Martin</i>								
	M _{st}				M _s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	1.14	0.29	0.56	1.72	0.71	0.36	0	1.42
date	0.99	0.31	0.38	1.61	0.93	0.48	0	1.87
date ²	-0.19	0.26	-0.71	0.32	0.42	0.53	-0.63	1.46
dur	0.66	0.25	0.17	1.14	0.52	0.23	0.06	0.98
<i>Whinchat</i>								
	M _{st}				M _s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	0.94	0.45	0.06	1.81	1.04	0.42	0.23	1.86
date	1.39	0.48	0.45	2.33	1.22	0.57	0.1	2.33
date ²	-0.55	0.37	-1.28	0.18	-0.7	0.33	-1.34	-0.06
dur	0.22	0.35	-0.47	0.9	0.05	0.35	-0.63	0.74
<i>Garden Warbler</i>								
	M _{st}				M _s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	0.16	0.2	-0.24	0.56	-0.15	0.21	-0.56	0.27
date	1.07	0.17	0.74	1.4	0.28	0.2	-0.12	0.67
date ²	-0.52	0.15	-0.81	-0.22	-0.2	0.2	-0.59	0.2
dur	0.34	0.17	0	0.67	0.36	0.16	0.06	0.67
<i>Lesser Whitethroat</i>								
	M _{st}				M _s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	0.76	0.27	0.23	1.29	0.34	0.27	-0.19	0.86

date	1.1	0.34	0.44	1.76	2.64	0.5	1.67	3.61
date ²	-0.96	0.22	-1.4	-0.52	-1.5	0.31	-2.1	-0.9
dur	0.18	0.2	-0.21	0.57	0.01	0.2	-0.39	0.4
Wood Warbler								
	M_{st}				M_s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	0.7	0.34	0.03	1.37	-0.77	0.51	-1.78	0.23
date	-0.3	0.34	-0.96	0.37	-4.15	1.79	-7.65	-0.65
date ²	-1.03	0.34	-1.7	-0.36	-3.68	1.48	-6.58	-0.78
dur	0.14	0.23	-0.3	0.59	0.17	0.23	-0.29	0.62
Spotted Flycatcher								
	M_{st}				M_s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	0.3	0.2	-0.1	0.7	-0.45	0.23	-0.91	0
date	1.22	0.18	0.86	1.58	0.17	0.22	-0.27	0.6
date ²	-0.92	0.18	-1.27	-0.56	-0.16	0.27	-0.68	0.37
dur	0.42	0.15	0.14	0.71	0.31	0.12	0.07	0.55
European Pied Flycatcher								
	M_{st}				M_s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	0.96	0.29	0.4	1.53	-0.66	0.46	-1.56	0.24
date	-0.37	0.3	-0.96	0.23	-2.97	1.47	-5.85	-0.1
date ²	-1.38	0.31	-1.99	-0.76	-2.4	1.17	-4.7	-0.1
dur	0	0.24	-0.47	0.47	0.18	0.22	-0.26	0.61
Red-backed Shrike								
	M_{st}				M_s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	0.75	0.32	0.12	1.38	-0.01	0.31	-0.62	0.61
date	1.31	0.3	0.72	1.9	0.72	0.43	-0.12	1.56
date ²	-0.97	0.31	-1.59	-0.36	0.32	0.55	-0.76	1.4
dur	0.21	0.25	-0.29	0.7	0.11	0.22	-0.33	0.54
Citril Finch								
	M_{st}				M_s			
Parameter	Est.	SE	L	U	Est.	SE	L	U
(Intercept)	0.53	0.3	-0.06	1.12	0.57	0.3	-0.02	1.16
date	0.38	0.3	-0.21	0.97	0.34	0.42	-0.49	1.17
date ²	-0.43	0.24	-0.9	0.05	-0.55	0.33	-1.21	0.1
dur	0.19	0.26	-0.33	0.71	0.09	0.28	-0.45	0.63

Figure S1: Predicted detection probability as a function of date (April 1=1) or survey duration (minutes) under model M_{st} (accounting for spatial and temporal variation in detection p) and

model M_s (accounting only for spatial variation in p) for 10 bird species sampled in 2014 across Switzerland. Shaded areas are 95% confidence intervals of predictions under M_{st} . Note that predictions under M_s are not expected to fall within confidence limits of M_{st} , because both use different predictor values (M_{st} : occasion specific value, M_s : averages over occasions).

Figure S2: Occupancy probability predictions for 266 sampled locations under model M_{st} (accounting for spatial and temporal variation in detection p) and model M_s (accounting only for spatial variation in p) for 10 bird species sampled in 2014 across Switzerland. Grey arrows are 95% confidence intervals (CI) of predictions under M_{st} . Red line is line of equivalence (if line is within the 95%CI, estimate under M_s is within 95%CI of M_{st}).

References

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